

PIDA: Persistent Identifiers for Semantic Artifacts

Reliably Addressing the Challenges of Persistent Semantic Artifact Referencing

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Abstract

The web of semantic artifacts, including glossaries, thesauri, ontologies, and knowledge graphs, increasingly relies on persistent and reliable referencing. For this, we offer PIDA (Persistent Identifiers for Semantic Artifacts) [1], a free of charge web-service to provide unique persistent URLs (PURLs) that can be used as internationalized resource identifiers (IRIs) within semantic artifacts. For almost two decades, persistent URLs have offered persistent access to digital objects, regardless of where they reside on the web [2].

PIDA is deployed with several key features such as enabled content negotiation of requests (client is able to negotiate a desirable representation of a resource with that server [3]), secured communication, periodic health checks of PURLs for broken links, automatic notification for the registrars about the artifact in question and at which point in time we registered problems, and logging of PURL activity and usage statistics, offering valuable insights into resource access and promoting transparency. PIDA team supports users in reviewing and creating redirection rules when creating PURLs.

Our robust service, deployed on sophisticated cloud infrastructure at the Jülich Supercomputing Center (JSC), guarantees high availability and long-term sustainability.

Keywords: Semantic Artifact, Persistent Identifiers, PURL, Content Negotiation

Resources

- Web service: <https://purls.helmholtz-metadaten.de/> “provide PURLs for semantic artifacts”

Author contributions

Conceptualization: VH, SF, MS, SS; Data Curation: SF; Funding acquisition: VH, SS; Methodology: SF, VH, MS; Project Administration: VH; Resources: VH, SS; Software: SF, MS; Su-

pervision: VH, SS; Writing – original draft: MS, SF, VH; Writing – review & editing: SF, MS, VH, SS.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

This project was developed at the Institute for Materials Data Science and Informatics (IAS-9) of the Jülich Research Center and funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC), an incubator-platform of the Helmholtz Association within the framework of the Information and Data Science strategic initiative.

Acknowledgments

We thank all users and members of the MIS group at FZJ for valuable discussions on the development of PIDA.

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